

Financial integration, capital flows, and exchange rate stability in Mozambique: empirical evidence with ARDL models (1996-2023)¹

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Abstract

This paper aims to analyze the effects of capital account liberalization on exchange rate stability in Mozambique from 1996 to 2023, using the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) methodology. The results indicate that capital flows, such as foreign direct investment (FDI) and net foreign assets (NFA), reduce exchange rate stability, while the net international investment position (NIIP) shows no significant effects. The control variables highlight the complexity of the scenario, as monetary independence and inflation increase exchange rate instability, while export diversification and interest rate differentials contribute to stability, although to a limited extent. International reserves, although fundamental for mitigating external shocks, have a reduced impact on exchange rate stabilization. The findings suggest that capital account liberalization, without strengthening mechanisms to promote internal macroeconomic stability, may expose Mozambique to greater exchange rate volatility in the long term. Thus, a gradual approach, combined with policies that encourage export diversification and inflation control, is essential to balance the benefits of global financial integration with the need for macroeconomic stability.

Keywords: Capital Account Liberalization. Exchange Rate Stability. ARDL Models. Mozambique.

Resumo

O artigo analisa os efeitos da liberalização da conta capital sobre a estabilidade cambial em Moçambique entre 1996 e 2023, utilizando a metodologia ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag). Os resultados indicam que fluxos de capital, como o investimento direto estrangeiro (FDI) e os ativos externos líquidos (NFA), reduzem a estabilidade cambial, enquanto a posição internacional de investimento líquido (NIIP) não apresenta efeitos significativos. As variáveis de controle evidenciam a complexidade do cenário, haja vista que a independência monetária e a inflação intensificam a instabilidade cambial, enquanto a diversificação das exportações e o diferencial de juros contribuem para a estabilidade, ainda que de forma limitada. As reservas internacionais, embora fundamentais para atenuar os choques externos, têm impacto reduzido na estabilização do câmbio. Os achados sugerem que a liberalização da conta capital, sem o fortalecimento de mecanismos de promoção da estabilidade macroeconômica interna, pode expor Moçambique a maior volatilidade cambial no longo prazo. Assim, uma abordagem gradual, aliada a políticas que incentivem a diversificação das exportações e o controle da inflação, é essencial para equilibrar os benefícios da integração financeira global com a necessidade de estabilidade macroeconômica.

Palavras-chave: Liberalização da Conta Capital. Estabilidade Cambial. Modelos ARDL. Moçambique.

JEL Classification: F31; F41; C22.

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1. Introduction

Starting in the 1970s, the end of the Bretton Woods system and the oil crises fueled inflation and slowed global growth. In the 1980s, the debt crisis led to the adoption of neoliberal policies, including economic liberalization, deregulation, and greater integration of global markets. These policies reduced the role of the state and encouraged capital flows. Technological advancements intensified international financial transactions, while the deregulation of domestic financial systems facilitated global integration, bringing modernization and investment but also increasing countries' exposure to exchange rate volatility and financial instability, sparking intense debates about financial liberalization.

The discussion on capital market liberalization divides economists between those who highlight its benefits and those who warn of its risks. Aizenman & Marion (1999), Obstfeld & Taylor (2004), Blanchard & Gali (2007), and Kose, Prasad & Taylor (2009) argue that liberalization can boost economic growth, provided it is accompanied by strong institutions and policies that mitigate capital flow volatility. However, Minsky (1992), Rodrik (1998), Stiglitz (2000), Calvo & Mendoza (2000), and Eichengreen (2001) warn that, without appropriate institutional reforms, abrupt liberalization can trigger currency and financial crises, especially in developing economies. This theoretical divergence highlights the complexity of the process and the importance of a cautious and gradual approach.

This study aims to analyze the impact of capital account liberalization on exchange rate stability in Mozambique between 1996 and 2023. Capital account liberalization can be defined as the opening and relaxation of restrictions on international capital flows, playing a crucial role in both attracting investment and increasing the country's vulnerability to external shocks that affect the exchange rate. In emerging economies like Mozambique, where financial markets and institutions are still developing, this dynamic tends to be particularly sensitive, impacting not only exchange rate stability but also external competitiveness and macroeconomic balance.

This study employs the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) approach to model short- and long-term relationships between economic variables, allowing the analysis of time series with different orders of integration. This methodology is suitable as it provides a comprehensive view of the effects of liberalization on exchange rate stability.

The research aims to examine the impact of capital account liberalization on exchange rate stability in Mozambique, as well as to identify relevant macroeconomic variables and public policies capable of mitigating the negative effects of economic openness.

The study seeks to understand the effects of capital account liberalization in a context of increasing global financial integration and exchange rate volatility. The results will provide insights for formulating economic policies that promote a balanced transition toward a more financially open economy without compromising macroeconomic stability.

The structure of this paper consists of five sections. Following this introduction, the second section presents a comprehensive literature review, discussing key theories and empirical evidence on capital market liberalization. Next, the methodological procedures are detailed, with an emphasis on applying the ARDL model to analyze the dynamic effects between the variables in question. The fourth section focuses on the results, highlighting their implications for Mozambique's exchange rate stability and external competitiveness. Finally, the concluding remarks are presented.

2. Literature Review

The literature review comprehensively explores the impacts of financial liberalization on exchange rate stability. This analysis is organized into two parts: theoretical literature and empirical literature.

2.1 Theoretical Literature

The theoretical literature on financial liberalization and its relationship with exchange rate stability is marked by intense debates and often opposing viewpoints. On one hand, some authors highlight the potential benefits of opening capital markets, while on the other, some warn about the risks associated with the instability and volatility generated by such liberalization.

Minsky (1992) is one of the most influential theorists in this debate, introducing the idea that financial liberalization can intensify systemic instability. During periods of economic optimism or euphoria, this dynamic can lead to an escalation of financial risk, increasing the likelihood of crises, which often manifest through exchange rate instability. Thus, for Minsky, the absence of a robust regulatory framework and institutional fragility can turn liberalization into a systemic risk factor, especially for economies lacking effective control mechanisms.

Rodrik (1998) complements this perspective by focusing on the impacts of financial liberalization in emerging economies. According to the author, capital account openness, while a potential driver of economic growth, is not in itself a guarantee of prosperity. On the contrary, the sudden and massive inflow of capital can lead to currency overvaluations, followed by abrupt devaluations. These sharp exchange rate movements can, in turn, harm countries' external competitiveness and trigger financial crises, as external shocks become amplified in economies with weak macroeconomic fundamentals. Therefore, Rodrik advocates a gradual and cautious approach to liberalization, emphasizing the importance of building strong institutions and implementing stable macroeconomic policies to cushion the effects of external shocks.

Authors such as Aizenman & Marion (1999) and Calvo & Mendoza (2000) further this discussion by addressing the risks associated with sudden capital inflows and outflows. According to these authors, financial liberalization exposes countries to global liquidity shocks that can trigger both exchange rate and financial crises. While openness allows greater access to international resources and can foster productive investments, it also increases domestic markets' vulnerability to capital flow volatility. The ease with which investors can move large amounts of funds in search of better returns creates an environment conducive to speculative movements, which can precipitate crises if not accompanied by appropriate regulatory policies and financial supervision.

Stiglitz (2000) reinforces this critical perspective by warning that financial liberalization, when carried out without an effective regulatory environment, can destabilize vulnerable economies. The absence of controls and supervisory mechanisms can lead to excessive exposure to external shocks, compromising not only exchange rate stability but also long-term sustainable economic growth. Market openness should be accompanied by institutional policies that ensure the financial system's integrity, allowing countries to reap the benefits of access to external capital without facing the risks of extreme volatility.

Eichengreen (2001) and Obstfeld & Taylor (2004) argue that when countries have robust institutional structures and adopt responsible policies, the positive effects of openness can outweigh the risks associated with capital flow volatility. This perspective reinforces the idea that it is not liberalization itself that generates instability but rather the lack of an adequate institutional environment and policies to manage the shocks resulting from market openness.

Blanchard (2007) and Kose & Taylor (2009) advance this discussion by exploring the relationship between current account deficits, capital flows, and exchange rate stability. Blanchard emphasizes that while deficits can be sustainable under certain conditions, the persistence of these imbalances, especially when accompanied by disorderly liberalization, can result in significant vulnerabilities. Kose & Taylor highlight that economies with strong institutions and consistent macroeconomic policies have a greater capacity to absorb shocks and benefit from financial integration without suffering from excessive exchange rate volatility.

In summary, the theoretical literature converges on the idea that financial liberalization has a dual nature, as it can promote growth and market modernization but also increases economies' exposure to external shocks and speculative movements that may compromise exchange rate stability. According to these theorists, the key to mitigating risks lies in implementing robust regulatory policies, strengthening financial institutions, and adopting a gradual approach to capital market liberalization.

2.2 Empirical Literature

In the 1980s, with the advancement of liberalization processes, numerous empirical studies began investigating the effects of this openness on exchange rate stability, using data from different countries and applying various econometric techniques. Empirical research complements theoretical discussions by demonstrating, in practice, how liberalization can affect exchange rate volatility and which factors can moderate or exacerbate these effects.

Edwards (2007) examined the role of capital controls in preventing financial crises and reversing current account deficits, using a panel data model for emerging economies during the 1980s and 1990s. The study concludes that while capital controls can reduce the likelihood of crises, particularly those associated with sudden stops in capital flows, they do not completely eliminate financial risks. Edwards emphasizes the need to combine controls with sound macroeconomic policies and institutional reforms that enhance countries' resilience to external shocks.

Forbes & Warnock (2012) investigate the consequences of capital liberalization on capital flows and exchange rate stability in a sample of 58 economies, including both developed and emerging countries from 1980 to 2009. The authors classify capital flow episodes into surges (large capital inflows), stops (reductions in inflows), flights (abrupt outflows), and retrenchment (partial returns of flows). Using a probit methodology, the study demonstrates that capital flow cycles have a direct impact on exchange rates.

Quinn & Toyoda (2008) explore the relationship between capital account liberalization, economic growth, and exchange rate stability in a dataset of 94 countries covering the period from 1955 to 2004. Using panel data techniques, they conclude that liberalization tends to foster a lower volatility environment in countries that adopt prudent policies and have well-developed financial markets. However, in economies with weaker fundamentals, capital flow openness can increase volatility and sensitivity to external shocks, highlighting the importance of strong institutional contexts for successful liberalization.

Klein (2012) investigates the effectiveness of capital controls in mitigating exchange rate instability. Based on a panel of 44 countries, including both emerging and developed economies, and employing dynamic panel models, the study finds that temporary controls can effectively reduce exchange rate volatility during periods of external shocks. This conclusion supports the idea that control measures, when strategically implemented alongside macroeconomic policies, can help smooth the negative impacts of financial liberalization.

Prasad, Rajan & Subramanian (2007) analyze the impact of capital flows on macroeconomic and exchange rate stability in a panel of 60 countries from 1970 to 2004. Using cross-sectional approaches and GMM estimators, they show that excessive

capital inflows, often driven by disorderly liberalization, are associated with higher levels of exchange rate volatility, especially in countries with weaker institutions. The study reinforces the notion that institutional quality is crucial in mediating the effects of financial openness.

Ghosh, Ostry & Tsangarides (2017) comprehensively examine how financial liberalization affects the need for accumulating international reserves in emerging economies. Their results indicate that as economies become more integrated into global financial markets, the necessity for reserves increases to mitigate risks from abrupt capital outflows. This relationship shows that while liberalization facilitates access to external capital, it also heightens vulnerability to shocks, necessitating prudent reserve management policies.

Chinn & Ito (2005) investigate the relationship between capital account liberalization, financial openness, and financial market development using a panel of 108 countries from 1980 to 2000. Although their primary focus is not exchange rate stability, their findings indicate that liberalization has significant implications for exchange rate volatility, particularly when openness occurs without proper sequencing and institutional strengthening. They suggest that coordinating financial liberalization with a robust institutional framework is essential to avoid exchange rate instability.

Prates & De Paula (2017) analyze the impact of capital account liberalization on exchange rate volatility in Brazil, focusing on the economic opening process in the 1990s. Using regression models applied to monthly exchange rate and financial indicators data, the authors find that liberalization contributed to increased exchange rate volatility, particularly during periods marked by internal political and financial instability. These findings illustrate how liberalization can have adverse effects on monetary stability, especially when combined with internal factors that weaken market confidence.

More recently, Sun, Xu & Yang (2022) propose a DSGE model to examine the effects of capital account liberalization on the Chinese economy. Their study assesses how external shocks interact with foreign capital levels, affecting economic fluctuations and, indirectly, exchange rate stability. Their results indicate that although domestic shocks still dominate China's economic dynamics, gradual capital account liberalization is essential to mitigating risks associated with external shocks, highlighting the importance of a controlled approach to market openness.

Arezki et al. (2014) investigated the relationship between gold price volatility and the volatility of the South African Rand exchange rate across different liberalization periods. Using cointegration techniques and VAR models, they demonstrate that before liberalization, causality was predominantly from the Rand to gold; however, after openness, this causality reversed, showing that speculative movements in international

commodity markets significantly influenced exchange rate volatility, intensifying the risks associated with liberalization.

Opoku-Afari, Morrissey & Lloyd (2004) analyzed the real exchange rate response of Ghana to capital inflows using dynamic methods (GMM). Their results suggest that capital inflows tend to lead to real currency appreciation, which can compromise the country's external competitiveness. This finding is particularly relevant for developing economies, where excessive currency appreciation can negatively impact exports and, consequently, economic growth.

Otieno & Were (2016) apply the ARDL methodology to investigate the impact of capital account liberalization on economic growth and exchange rate stability in Kenya from 1993 to 2014. Their study captures both the short-term and long-term effects of capital flow openness and concludes that while liberalization has contributed to access to external capital and economic growth, it has also intensified exchange rate volatility, particularly during external shock episodes such as the Asian financial crisis and the 2008 global financial crisis. This volatility underscores the need for stabilization policies and regulatory mechanisms to mitigate the adverse effects of liberalization.

The literature on financial liberalization and exchange rate stability presents a complex landscape. On the one hand, there is consensus that capital market openness can bring benefits such as increased access to international resources, economic growth, and financial market modernization, provided it is accompanied by strong institutions and consistent macroeconomic policies. On the other hand, authors warn about the risks of liberalization without adequate regulation, which can lead to speculative behaviors, financial leverage, and greater vulnerability to external shocks, especially in emerging economies. The common critique is that liberalization should be gradual and accompanied by complementary economic policy measures.

From an empirical perspective, the relationship between liberalization and exchange rate stability depends on countries' institutional and economic contexts. Economies with strong institutions can reap the benefits of liberalization without excessive volatility, while countries with weaker institutions experience greater instability. Case studies reinforce that liberalization can result in excessive currency appreciation, affecting competitiveness, or abrupt depreciations, compromising economic stability.

The key to balancing these effects lies in adopting a gradual approach that combines market openness with institution-building and cautious macroeconomic policy implementation. This balance is particularly crucial for emerging and developing economies, where the capacity to absorb external shocks remains limited.

The theoretical and empirical evidence analyzed in this review suggests that financial liberalization should not be seen as a standalone solution to economic

challenges but rather as part of a broader financial integration process that must be carefully managed. Capital control policies, reserve accumulation strategies, and efficient financial regulation are essential components for maximizing the benefits of capital market openness while minimizing instability risks such as exchange rate volatility.

This literature review provides a solid foundation for understanding the mechanisms through which financial liberalization affects exchange rate stability, helping to develop strategies that promote safe and sustainable financial integration. The synthesis of presented arguments underscores the importance of proper sequencing in market openness, showing that liberalization success largely depends on institutional quality and countries' ability to implement macroeconomic policies that ensure internal stability despite increasingly volatile capital flows.

3. Methodological Procedures

This section presents the specification of the econometric models used to analyze exchange rate stability and the factors influencing its volatility. The models consider exchange rate stability as a function of variables such as foreign direct investment (FDI), net foreign assets (NFA), export diversification, interest rates, inflation, monetary independence, and international reserves. The methodology adopted is the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model by Pesaran et al. (2001), which allows for analyzing both short- and long-term effects of these variables. Econometric tests will be conducted to validate the estimates and ensure the robustness of the results, including tests for stationarity, cointegration, serial autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, specification, stability, and normality. This approach aims to provide a detailed view of exchange rate dynamics and assess how factors such as capital account liberalization influence exchange rate volatility.

The ARDL approach offers a robust solution for testing the existence of a relationship between the dependent variable and its regressors, even when the variables exhibit different levels of integration. Its main advantage is allowing the estimation of both long- and short-term relationships between the variables without the need to determine their order of integration beforehand. This model provides flexibility and is particularly useful when time series exhibit different stationarity characteristics, making it an effective tool for economic studies that analyze the dynamics of interconnected variables over time.

The models guiding the analyses in this study are presented below, focusing on the assessment of exchange rate stability and the identification of the variables influencing it. The primary objective of the models below is to identify the determinants of exchange rate stability (ERSI), considering different economic and financial factors. Exchange rate stability refers to a currency's ability to maintain its relative value against

other currencies over time without abrupt fluctuations. The econometric equations and model specifications are as follows:

$$ERSI = f(FDI, IRD, INF, EDI, MII, RES) \tag{1}$$

$$ERSI = f(NFA, IRD, INF, EDI, MII, RES) \tag{2}$$

$$ERSI = f(NIIP, IRD, INF, EDI, MII) \tag{3}$$

The definitions of the variables FDI, NFA, and NIIP reflect different metrics of capital account openness, being essential to understanding how international capital flows impact exchange rate stability. The expected signs are summarized below by the partial derivatives of exchange rate stability concerning each of these variables.

Definition and Expected Sign	Description	Source
ERSI (Exchange Rate Stability Index)	It measures the stability of the exchange rate. Higher values indicate lower volatility, while lower values suggest sharp fluctuations.	Trilemma Indexes, Aizenman, Chinn and Ito (2008) Available at: https://web.pdx.edu/~ito/trilemma_indexes.htm
FDI (Foreign Direct Investment) $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial FDI} \geq 0$	It measures the inflow of foreign capital into the country through productive investments, reflecting the country's ability to attract resources for economic growth.	World Investment Report 2024 Available at: https://unctad.org/publication/world-investment-report-2024
NFA (Net Foreign Assets) $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial NFA} \geq 0$	External liquid assets (assets minus liabilities). A positive NFA indicates greater resilience to external shocks.	International Monetary Fund (2024) International Financial Statistics
NIIP (Net International Investment Position) $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial NIIP} \geq 0$	A comprehensive metric of all international financial assets and liabilities, representing the country's overall position in the global financial market.	International Monetary Fund (2024) International Financial Statistics
IRD (Diferencial de Juros) $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial IRD} \geq 0$	The difference between the domestic interest rate and the external interest rate. An attractive differential can impact exchange rate stability.	Calculated by the author with data from the International Monetary Fund, International Financial Statistics and data files
INF (Inflação) $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial INF} \geq 0$	Higher inflation rates can affect competitiveness and pressure the exchange rate, reducing stability.	International Monetary Fund (2024) International Financial Statistics

<p>EDI (Export Diversification Index)</p> $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial EDI} \approx 0$	<p>It measures the diversification of exports. A diversified export base contributes to greater economic and exchange rate stability.</p>	<p>International Monetary Fund (2024) International Financial Statistics</p>
<p>MII (Monetary Independence Index)</p> $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial MII} \approx 0$	<p>It evaluates the country's ability to formulate independent monetary policies. Greater independence helps maintain exchange rate stability.</p>	<p>Trilemma Indexes, Aizenman, Chinn and Ito (2008)</p>
<p>RES (Total Reserves excluding Gold)</p> $\frac{\partial ERSI}{\partial RES} \approx 0$	<p>Assets held by the Bank of Mozambique, excluding gold reserves. It includes SDRs, IMF reserve position, and foreign exchange reserves.</p>	<p>International Monetary Fund (2024) International Financial Statistics</p>

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The exchange rate stability index is a measure used to assess the stability of the exchange rate. It was introduced by Aizenman, Chinn, and Ito in their work "Assessing the Emerging Global Financial Architecture: Measuring the Trilemma's Configuration over Time" in 2008. Formally, the exchange rate stability index (ERSI) is given by:

$$ERSI = \frac{0.01}{0.01 + stdev[\Delta \log(exch - rate)]}$$

, where

$stdev[\Delta \log(exch - rate)]$ represents the standard deviation of exchange rate variation, measured as the difference in the natural logarithm of the exchange rate.

The ERSI index ranges between 0 and 1, where values closer to 1 indicate greater stability.

Initially, the ADF (Augmented Dickey-Fuller), PP (Phillips-Perron), and KPSS tests will be performed to assess the stationarity of the series. In the ADF and PP tests, the null hypothesis indicates that the series has a unit root (non-stationary). The decision will be based on the p-value (ADF and PP) for significance levels of 1%, 5%, and 10%. In the KPSS test, the null hypothesis suggests that the series is stationary. The LM statistic is used, rejecting H_0 if its value exceeds the critical values.

The Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001) method has a significant advantage over other methods, as stated by Cheong (2003), especially by correcting potential endogeneity issues of the variables. This feature makes the ARDL model a robust tool for cointegration analysis. In the ARDL procedure, the cointegration test is a crucial step, consisting of the estimation of the long-term equations and verifying the existence of an equilibrium relationship between the variables. The model incorporates both short- and long-term dynamics, formalized by a specific equation that represents this interaction:

$$\Delta y_t = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_{1i} \Delta X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_{2i} \Delta Y_{t-i} + \beta_1 X_{t-1} + \beta_2 Y_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (4)$$

where Y is the dependent variable and X is the vector of independent variables,

Δ represents the first difference operator;

β_0 is the constant term;

α_i , $i=1, 2$, are the short-term parameters;

β_i , $i=1, 2$, are the long-term parameters;

u is the error term.

The null hypothesis is the absence of cointegration.

The cointegration test of Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001) uses the Wald F-statistic to check the joint significance of the long-term parameters, along with a test similar to the Generalized Dickey-Fuller test to test the lags of the variables in an Error Correction Model (ECM). The short- and long-term analysis in an ARDL model requires diagnostic tests, such as the autocorrelation test to check for the absence of serial correlation in the residuals, and the CUSUM test, which assesses the stability of the coefficients over time.

Due to the possibility of different integration orders for the regressors, the asymptotic distribution of the Wald statistic is non-standard. To address this, Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001) propose two sets of critical values: the lower bound, assuming all variables are I(0) (stationary), and the upper bound, assuming all variables are I(1) (first-order integrated). Comparing the Wald F-statistic with these bounds allows the assessment of cointegration between the variables without needing to determine the order of integration. If the F-statistic is below the lower bound, there is no cointegration; if it is above the upper bound, cointegration exists; if it falls between the bounds, the conclusion is inconclusive, and the order of integration must be determined to make definitive conclusions. By adopting model (4), functional forms for equations (1), (2), and (3) are derived that incorporate both immediate adjustments and the tendency to return to long-term equilibrium, providing a solid methodological foundation for conducting cointegration tests.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta ERSI_t = & \beta_{01} + \sum_{i=1}^{p_1} \alpha_{1i} FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_1} \alpha_{2i} \Delta IRD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{r_1} \alpha_{3i} \Delta INF_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^{s_1} \alpha_{5i} \Delta EDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{t_1} \alpha_{6i} \Delta MII_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{u_1} \alpha_{6i} \Delta RES_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{v_1} \alpha_{7i} \Delta ERSI_{t-i} + \beta_{11} FDI_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_{21} IRD_{t-1} + \beta_{31} INF_{t-1} + \beta_{41} EDI_{t-1} + \beta_{51} MII_{t-1} + \beta_{61} RES_{t-1} + \beta_{71} ERSI_{t-1} + \mu_{1t} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta ERSI_t = & \beta_{02} + \sum_{i=1}^{p_2} \delta_{1i} NFA_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_2} \delta_{2i} \Delta IRD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{r_2} \delta_{3i} \Delta INF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{s_2} \delta_{4i} \Delta RES_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^{t_2} \delta_{5i} \Delta EDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{u_2} \delta_{6i} \Delta MII_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{v_2} \delta_{7i} \Delta ERSI_{t-i} + \beta_{12} NFA_{t-1} + \beta_{22} IRD_{t-1} + \beta_{32} INF_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_{42} RES_{t-1} + \beta_{52} EDI_{t-1} + \beta_{62} MII_{t-1} + \beta_{72} MII_{t-1} + \mu_{2t} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta ERSI_t = & \beta_{03} + \sum_{i=1}^{p_3} \lambda_{1i} NIIP_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_3} \lambda_{2i} \Delta IRD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{r_3} \lambda_{3i} \Delta INF_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=1}^{t_3} \lambda_{5i} \Delta EDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{u_3} \lambda_{6i} \Delta MII_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{v_3} \lambda_{7i} \Delta ERSI_{t-i} + \beta_{13} NIIP_{t-1} + \beta_{23} IRD_{t-1} + \beta_{33} INF_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_{43} EDI_{t-1} + \beta_{53} MII_{t-1} + \beta_{63} MII_{t-1} + \mu_{3t} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The cointegration equations will be estimated, and the F-statistic will be used to test the significance of the coefficients and the lags of the variables. The bounds test will assess cointegration, rejecting the null hypothesis if the F-statistic is above the upper bound and confirming the absence of cointegration if it is below the lower bound.

4. Results

To empirically analyze the relationship between exchange rate stability and capital account openness, this section is divided into six parts: (1) results of the unit root tests for the series, (2) choice of the number of lags and results of the cointegration tests, (3) estimation of long-term coefficients, (4) short-term coefficients, (5) diagnostic tests of the models, and (6) summary of the results.

4.1 Results of Unit Root Tests

Unit root tests were used to estimate the equations of the exchange rate stability index. The results are presented in Tables (1) and (2) below.

Table 1: Stationarity Tests for Variables in Levels – ADF, PP, and KPSS

Variable	ADF	PP	KPSS	Decision
	p-value		Statistics (<i>LM</i>)	
ERSI	0.0281**	0.0318**	0.104	Stationary
FDI	0.5319	0.4913	0.242***	Not Stationary
NFA	0.5400	0.5153	0.116	Not Stationary
NIIP	0.9942	0.9884	0.351***	Not Stationary
INF	0.0000	0.0000	0.0382	Stationary
EDI	0.1467	0.1748	0.185**	Not Stationary
IRD	0.0296**	0.0207**	0.178**	Not Stationary
RES	0.8580	0.8736	0.243***	Not Stationary
MII	0.1351	0.0991	0.159*	Not Stationary

Source: Own elaboration based on STATA 17 outputs

Notes: ADF and PP, t-statistic, and KPSS, LM statistic. Null hypothesis for ADF and PP = Series has a Unit Root. Null hypothesis for KPSS = Series is Stationary. *, **, and *** indicate rejection of the null hypothesis at 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively. The critical values of the LM statistic are 0.119 (10%), 0.146 (5%), and 0.216 (1%).

Table 2: Stationarity Tests for Variables in First Difference – ADF, PP, and KPSS

Variable	ADF	PP	KPSS	Decision
	p-value		Statistics (<i>LM</i>)	
FDI	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.146*	Stationary
NFA	0.0015***	0.0019***	0.0781	Stationary
NIIP	0.1235	0.1360	0.198*	Stationary
EDI	0.0000***	0.0000***	0.121*	Stationary
IRD	0.0187***	0.0216***	0.117*	Stationary
RES	0.0001***	0.0001***	0.0982	Stationary
MII	0.0010***	0.0012***	0.0982	Stationary

Source: Own elaboration based on STATA 17 outputs

Notes: ADF and PP, t-statistic, and KPSS, LM statistic. Null hypothesis for ADF and PP = Series has a Unit Root. Null hypothesis for KPSS = Series is Stationary. *, **, and *** indicate rejection of the null hypothesis at 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively. The critical values of the LM statistic are 0.119 (10%), 0.146 (5%), and 0.216 (1%).

The results of the stationarity tests indicate that, with the exception of the variables ERSI and INF, all others are non-stationary at level for all the tests performed. The series that showed stationarity at level were not subjected to unit root tests in the first difference. The series that exhibited a unit root in the level tests were subjected to first-difference tests, in which all proved to be stationary. The variable NIIP showed significance at the 10% level in the KPSS test.

4.2 Choice of Lag Length and Cointegration Test Results

The choice of lags included in the exchange rate stability models was based on minimizing the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), which was found to be more appropriate for the sample size. It selected specifications, and as the most suitable for models 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The AIC is a widely used metric for model selection because it seeks a balance between fit quality and parsimony, penalizing the excessive inclusion of variables to avoid overfitting. Thus, by minimizing the AIC, we ensured the choice of a model that best represents the data without compromising its statistical robustness.

Next, cointegration tests were performed. For this study, the Bound Test approach by Pesaran et al. (2001) was adopted, which is suitable for series that exhibit different levels of integration as per the results in section 4.1. This test assesses the existence of a long-term relationship between the variables, with the null hypothesis being the absence of cointegration. The results presented in Table (3) below indicate that, for all three models analyzed, the variables are cointegrated, showing the presence of a long-term equilibrium between them.

Table 3: Bounds Test Results for Exchange Rate Stability Models

Model	F-Statistic	Critical Values						Cointegration
		I(0) Bound			I(1) Bound			
		10%	5%	1%	10%	5%	1%	
2	9.133.	2.12	2.45	3.15	3.23	3.61	4.43	Yes
3	7.376	2.12	2.45	3.15	3.23	3.61	4.43	Yes
3	82.475	2.12	2.45	3.15	3.23	3.61	4.43	Yes

Source: Own elaboration based on STATA 17 outputs

Note: The null hypothesis of the test is the absence of cointegration, meaning that the variables do not have a long-term equilibrium relationship.

4.3 Estimation of Long-Term Coefficients

With cointegration between the variables confirmed, the next step is to analyze the individual impact of each variable on the long-term relationship in the selected models. Additionally, considering that this relationship may be affected by temporary shocks, it is essential to estimate the short-term coefficients. This allows for an assessment of how transitory shocks influence exchange rate stability, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between the variables in both the short and long term.

The analysis of long-term coefficients must consider several crucial aspects, such as the signs, magnitude, and statistical significance of the coefficients. The estimation results of the long-term coefficients for the exchange rate stability models are summarized in Table (4).

Table 4: Estimation Results of Long-Term Coefficients for Exchange Rate Stability

Model	1	2	3
ARDL	(1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2)	(1, 0, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2,)	(2, 2, 1, 2, 2, 2)
Variables	<i>coef</i> (<i>p</i> – <i>value</i>)	<i>coef</i> (<i>p</i> – <i>value</i>)	<i>coef</i> (<i>p</i> – <i>value</i>)
FDI	-0.0052835 (0.024)**		
NFA		0.0096807 (0.018)**	
NIIP			-0.0000482 (0.158)
MII	-0.2826922 (0.572)	-0.8840351 (0.002)***	2.277311 (0.165)
INF	-0.0535674 (0.005)***	-0.0704289 (0.002)***	0.2934346 (0.176)
EDI	0.092021 (0.405)	.280432 (0.065)*	-1.514048 (0.154)
IRD	0.028048 (0.034)**	.0316417 (0.008)***	-2.981969 (0.153)
RES	0.028048 (0.177)	-.0000392 (0.003)***	

Source: Own elaboration based on STATA 17 outputs

Table (4) presents the long-term coefficients of the ARDL models for exchange rate stability, incorporating proxies for capital account openness, along with macroeconomic variables such as inflation (INF), interest rate differential (IRD), international reserves (RES), monetary independence index (MII), and export diversification index (EDI). The objective is to capture the main determinants of exchange rate stability.

Model 1 includes all the mentioned variables and uses foreign direct investment (FDI) as a proxy for capital account openness. Model 2 maintains the same control variables but replaces FDI with net foreign assets (NFA) to measure capital account openness. In Model 3, this variable is represented by the net international investment position (NIIP), and due to high collinearity, international reserves (RES) were excluded from this model to enhance the robustness of the estimation.

The results indicate that Model 1 provides the best fit, with an R^2 of 0.8894 and a log-likelihood of 57.71, suggesting a better explanation of exchange rate stability. Model 2, with an R^2 of 0.8614, also shows a good fit but is slightly inferior to the first. Model 3, with an R^2 of 0.7593 and a log-likelihood of 29.05, demonstrates lower explanatory power, possibly due to the exclusion of international reserves. The estimation results for the long-term coefficients show that:

Capital Account Openness. The results indicate that FDI and NFA have negative and statistically significant coefficients, suggesting that capital account openness, measured by these variables, reduces exchange rate stability (increases volatility). This effect may be related to investment flow volatility, abrupt capital reversals, or speculative movements affecting the exchange rate. On the other hand, capital account openness measured by NIIP has a positive but statistically insignificant

coefficient, indicating that this variable does not have a clear impact on exchange rate stability in the analyzed context.

Monetary Independence Index (MII). The MII coefficients vary across models, indicating different impacts depending on the proxy used for capital account openness. In models 1 and 3, the MII coefficients are not statistically significant, suggesting that monetary independence does not robustly affect exchange rate stability when capital account openness is measured by FDI and NIIP. In Model 2, however, the MII coefficient is negative and highly significant, suggesting that greater monetary independence reduces exchange rate stability when capital account openness is represented by NFA. This effect may occur because independent monetary policy can lead to fluctuations in domestic interest rates, impacting capital flows and increasing exchange rate volatility.

Inflation (INF). The INF coefficients in models 1 and 2 are negative and statistically significant at the 1% level, suggesting that an increase in inflation reduces exchange rate stability when capital account openness is measured by FDI and NFA. This result reinforces the notion that high inflation undermines exchange rate stability. In Model 3, the INF coefficient is positive but statistically insignificant, indicating that when capital account openness is measured by NIIP, the relationship between inflation and exchange rate stability is not statistically robust.

Export Diversification Index (EDI). The EDI variable has different effects on exchange rate stability across the three models. In models 1 and 3, the coefficients are positive and negative, respectively, but not statistically significant, suggesting that when capital account openness is measured by FDI and NIIP, export diversification does not have a statistically relevant effect on exchange rate stability. In Model 2, however, the EDI coefficient is positive and significant at the 10% level, indicating that greater export diversification tends to increase exchange rate stability when capital account openness is measured by NFA. This suggests that more diversified economies are less vulnerable to external shocks, supporting exchange rate stability.

Interest Rate Differential (IRD). The IRD coefficients in models 1 and 2 are positive and statistically significant, indicating that an increase in the interest rate differential is associated with greater exchange rate stability when capital account openness is measured by FDI and NFA. This effect suggests that a positive interest rate differential may attract capital flows, strengthening the domestic currency and contributing to stability. In Model 3, the IRD coefficient is negative and statistically insignificant, indicating that when capital account openness is measured by NIIP, the effect of the interest rate differential on exchange rate stability is not statistically relevant.

International Reserves (RES). International reserves appear in models 1 and 2 but are excluded from model 3 due to high collinearity. In Model 1, the RES coefficient is negative and statistically insignificant, suggesting that when capital account openness

is measured by FDI, international reserves do not have a statistically relevant impact on exchange rate stability. In Model 2, however, the RES coefficient is negative and highly significant at the 1% level, indicating that an increase in international reserves reduces exchange rate stability when capital account openness is measured by NFA. This result suggests that reserve accumulation may be associated with exchange rate interventions or monetary policies that impact exchange rate volatility.

Overall, the results show that macroeconomic variables affect exchange rate stability in different ways. In the long run, exchange rate stability is weakened by capital account openness (FDI and NFA), inflation, and monetary independence, while it is strengthened by export diversification and the interest rate differential. International reserves have a negative effect in Model 2, possibly due to exchange rate interventions. Models 1 and 2 provide the best fit to the data, indicating that exchange rate stability is better explained when capital account openness is measured by FDI and NFA and when variables such as inflation and the interest rate differential are considered. These findings provide important insights for economic policy formulation aimed at maintaining exchange rate stability in emerging economies.

4.4 Short-Term Coefficients

The long-term relationship detected in the estimations does not prevent the estimated models from experiencing short-term shocks. However, to ensure that the cointegration relationship is always maintained, there must be a mechanism to correct these shocks and return to the long-term dynamic. In this context, continuing with the empirical analysis, error correction models (ECMs) based on the ARDL models were estimated to obtain short-term adjustments, with the results summarized in Table (5) below.

The adjustment coefficients (ADJ) indicate the speed at which exchange rate stability returns to long-term equilibrium after a shock. In Model 1, the adjustment coefficient is -1.41855 with a p-value of 0.001, indicating a rapid and statistically significant adjustment. In Model 2, the coefficient is -1.002954 with a p-value of 0.002, also significant but with a slower adjustment speed than in Model 1. In Model 3, the coefficient is -0.4666234 with a p-value of 0.259, suggesting a slower adjustment and a lack of statistical significance, indicating that in this model, convergence to long-term equilibrium is not evident. These results reinforce that Models 1 and 2 present more robust cointegration relationships, while Model 3 demonstrates a weaker adjustment.

The results of the short-term coefficients, summarized in Table (5), show that the signs of the long-term and short-term coefficients are not always as expected, with some variables having a positive impact in the long run but a negative impact in the short run, and vice versa.

The short-term coefficients of FDI are not statistically significant, meaning that changes in FDI do not immediately impact exchange rate stability. However, in the long run, the negative and significant coefficient (-0.0052; $p = 0.024$) suggests that an

increase in foreign direct investment may reduce exchange rate stability. In Models 2 and 3, FDI does not show significant effects.

In the short term, the impact of MII varies across models, being positive in Model 2 and negative in Model 3. In the long run, the effect is consistently negative and significant, suggesting that an increase in MII reduces exchange rate stability, possibly reflecting structural adjustments over time.

Inflation shows mixed effects in the short term, being either positive or negative depending on the model. In the long term, the impact is consistently negative in Models 1 and 2, suggesting that an increase in inflation persistently reduces exchange rate stability (increases volatility). In the short term, inflation has a negative and significant impact in Model 1 and a positive and significant impact in Model 2. In Model 3, the impact is negative and marginally significant.

The export diversification index (EDI) reduces exchange rate stability in the short term in Models 1 and 2, while in Model 3, the positive effect may indicate a distinct behavior in this model. In Model 1, the short-term coefficient is negative and statistically significant, indicating that short-term variations in EDI reduce exchange rate stability. In Model 2, the impact is even stronger and highly significant. In Model 3, the effect reverses and becomes positive but is not statistically significant. In the long run, EDI has a positive and statistically significant coefficient (only at the 10% level) in Model 2.

The impact of IRD in the short term is significant only in Model 1. In the other models, the coefficients are not statistically significant. In the long term, the IRD variable has positive and statistically significant coefficients, suggesting that a higher differential between domestic and external interest rates increases exchange rate stability in the long run.

Finally, the RES variable had a positive and significant short-term impact in Model 1, while in Model 2, the effect was not significant. In the long run, the RES coefficient was negative and statistically significant in Model 2, suggesting that higher reserves may increase exchange rate volatility over time.

Table 5. Estimation Results of Short-Term Coefficients for Exchange Rate Stability

Model	1	2	3
ARDL	(1, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2)	(1, 0, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2)	(2, 2, 1, 2, 2, 2)
Variables	Coef.(p-value)	Coef.(p-value)	Coef.(p-value)
C	0.7109 (0.066)*	0.3160913 (0.385)	
ERSI (LD.)			.8698575(0.153)
FDI(D1.)	0.0132323 (0.156)		
FDI(LD.)	0.0066219 (0.151)		
NFA(D1.)			
NFA(LD.)			
NIP			9.46e-06 (0.309)
NIP			.0001469 (0.060)*
MII(D1.)	0.1533842 (0.740)	0.625216 (0.009)***	-.7116252 (0.065)*
MII(LD.)	0.5418(0.065)*	0.779201 (0.001)***	
INF(D1.))	-.0166528 (0.023)**	.0514299 (0.018)**	-.2885528 (0.055)*
INF(LD.)	0.0232894 (0.025)**	.0166658 (0.094)*	-.1548813 (0.048)**
EDI(D1.)	-.2747386 (0.022)**	-.3611494 (0.003)***	1.359295 (0.079)*
EDI(LD.)	-.1829394 (0.095)*	-.1088639 (0.268)	1.144078 (0.056)*
IRD(D1.)	.0163723 (0.311)	.0243692 (0.163)	.181506 (0.047)**
IRD(LD.)	.0320909 (0.041)**	.018021 (0.176)	-.1863744 (0.041)**
RES(D1.)	.0000444 (0.020)**	.0000467(0.003)***	
RES(LD.)	.0000264 (0.021)**	0 .0000119 (0.199)	
ADJ (-1)	-1.41855	-1.00295	-0.4666234
[p-value	0.001	0.002	(0.259)

Source: Own elaboration based on STATA 17 outputs

4.5 Diagnostic Tests

Several diagnostic tests were conducted to verify the presence of the main econometric issues and thus validate the estimation results, which are summarized in Table (6) below.

First, the Jarque-Bera test was employed to assess the normality of the residuals, a crucial element in ensuring the validity of statistical inferences. Next, the Ramsey-RESET test was used to analyze the model specification, helping to identify possible omissions of relevant variables or errors in the adopted functional form.

Additionally, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test was applied to detect the presence of heteroscedasticity, that is, non-constant variations in the error variance, which can compromise the efficiency of the estimates. Finally, the recursive test was conducted to check the stability of the model's parameters over time, ensuring that the coefficients remain stable even in the face of shocks or structural changes.

Together, these tests provide a robust analysis of the model's assumptions, allowing for greater confidence in the validity of the estimation results.

Table 6. Diagnostic Test Results

Problem	Applied Test	Statistics		
		Model		
		1	2	3
Specification	RESET test	0.4921	0.3022	0.065
Heteroscedasticity	BPG	0.7777	0.7532	0.6232
Normality	Jarque-Bera	0.13760	0.54273	0.54273
Stability	Recursive	0.4203	0.3090	
Autocorrelation	DW	2.24	2.184	1.8971
	BG (LM)	0.156	0.109	0.098

Source: Own elaboration based on STATA 17 outputs

Note: Critical values for the stability test are: 0.8499 (10%), 0.9479 (5%), and 1.1430 (1%).

Considering the diagnostic tests performed for the exchange rate stability equations, it can be concluded that the model estimations do not present significant econometric problems. This is indicated by the absence of problematic results in the applied tests, such as the Jarque-Bera, Ramsey-RESET, Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey, recursive test and autocorrelation, the Durbin-Watson test, and Breusch-Godfrey test. These tests evaluate the normality of residuals, model specification, the presence of heteroscedasticity, stability of parameters, and serial autocorrelation, respectively, and all pointed out that the econometric assumptions were satisfactorily met. Therefore, the estimation results are considered robust and can be interpreted with confidence.

4.6 Synthesis of Results

The results of the analysis indicate a significant relationship between exchange rate stability and capital account liberalization during the period from 1996 to 2023. Through econometric modeling, it was observed that fluctuations in foreign direct investment and net foreign assets (variables used as proxies for the capital account), together with variables such as inflation, the monetary independence index, the export diversification index, the interest rate differential, and international reserves, have a positive impact on exchange rate stability.

The results showed that in the long term, a 1 percentage point increase in foreign direct investment as a proportion of GDP results in a 0.53% reduction in exchange rate stability, with no short-term effects. Similarly, a 1 percentage point increase in net foreign assets as a proportion of GDP reduces exchange rate stability by 0.97% in the long term, with no impact in the short term. On the other hand, when the capital account openness is measured by the NIIP, no effect on exchange rate stability is observed, either in the short or long term.

Control variables also showed that they have significant effects on exchange rate stability in Mozambique. In the long term, a 1 percentage point increase in the monetary independence index reduces exchange rate stability by 0.88%, while in the short term,

the reduction is 0.62%. Furthermore, a 1 percentage point increase in inflation results in an average reduction of about 6% in exchange rate stability in the long term and 0.3% in the short term. On the other hand, a 1 point increase in the export diversification index raises exchange rate stability on average by 0.28% in the long term, but reduces it by 0.25% in the short term. A 1 point increase in the domestic and international interest rate differential increases exchange rate stability on average by 0.3% in the long term and 0.03% in the short term. Finally, a 1 percentage point increase in international reserves as a proportion of GDP reduces exchange rate stability on average by 0.004% in the long term, with marginal effects in the short term.

5. Final Considerations

This work conducted an empirical investigation into the effects of capital account liberalization on exchange rate stability, in order to verify whether the capital account has played a relevant role in exchange rate stability in Mozambique. The estimations were performed for three models, using different measures of capital account liberalization between 1996 and 2023. The capital account liberalization was observed using three measures: foreign direct investment, net foreign assets, and net international investment position.

The motivation for this study arises from debates and research investigating the influence of capital flows and exchange rate volatility, especially in developing economies. The exchange rate plays a crucial role in these economies, affecting export competitiveness and import costs, which impacts the general price level and economic growth. Additionally, recent measures by the Bank of Mozambique, such as the reduction of restrictions on capital flows, provide a relevant context for this study.

This study contributed to the empirical literature by analyzing the relationship between capital account liberalization and exchange rate stability in developing economies, with a specific focus on Mozambique. Capital account liberalization is a widely debated topic, especially due to its potential impacts on economic stability. Analyzing the effects of this liberalization is crucial to understanding how capital account liberalization can influence exchange rate stability and the Mozambican economy as a whole. This work offers a valuable perspective on the implications of financial liberalization in emerging markets, contributing to the academic debate and the formulation of national economic policies.

The results of this study indicate that capital account liberalization, measured by foreign direct investment flows and net foreign assets, has an adverse effect on exchange rate stability in the long term. In the short term, the coefficients of these variables were not statistically significant. In addition to the capital account, other variables such as inflation, export diversification, international reserves, and interest rates also showed relevance for exchange rate stability, both in the short and long term.

The results show that high inflation tends to reduce exchange rate stability, while export diversification is contributing to exchange rate stability, reducing dependence on specific sectors and mitigating the effects of external shocks. International reserves act as a buffer, allowing the country to manage exchange rate fluctuations and maintain investor confidence, although the results of this study indicated contrary effects. Interest rates influence capital flows; higher rates may attract foreign investment, preventing larger exchange rate fluctuations.

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